

Table 2. Performance of IET7564 and IET7566 in direct-seeded upland trials at different locations.

Variety	Kanke	Tuljapur	Dehradun	Rewa	Varanasi	Derol	Barchara (Cuttack)	Hazaribagh
IET7564								
Yield (t/ha)	1.7	1.0	1.2	2.2	1.5	1.4	1.4	2.4
Days to flowering	64	64	68	61	67	56	68	57
IET7566								
Yield (t/ha)	2.0	1.0	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.7	1.5	2.7
Days to flowering	64	65	80	65	69	64	75	65
Local check ^a								
Yield (t/ha)	1.4	1.0	0.5	2.0	1.5	1.6	—	1.4
Days to flowering	83	85	14	65	64	69	—	72
Seeding date	2 Jul 1982	—	20 Jun 1982	16 Jul 1982	21 Jul 1982	11 Jul 1982	13 Jun 1982	7 Jul 1982
Total rainfall (mm)	749	545.9	859.8	1259	851.3	656.0	765	714.5
Rainy days (no.)	59	45	44	44	40	24	41	—
Drought spell (Stage)	Vegetative	Vegetative	Vegetative	—	—	Vegetative	Vegetative	Vegetative

^a The local check was RAU4045 at Kanke, Tuljapur 1 at Tuljapur, Ramjawain at Dehradun, RWR212 at Rewa, Bakki at Varanasi, Sathi 5436 at Derol, and Brown gora at Hazaribagh.

check varieties in direct-seeded and transplanted conditions. They matured earlier, showed BI resistance, had good drought tolerance (days to wilting), and possessed seed dormancy. IET7564, IET7633, IET7635, and IET7261 are resistant to RTV (Table 1). All cultures were entered in the national program. In 1982 kharif, IET7564 and IET7566 were evaluated at other research centers (Table 2).

In demonstration plots (200 m²) at AICRIP, direct-seeded IET7564 and IET7566 matured in 90 and 95 days and yielded 3.7 and 4.7 t/ha. IET7564 ranked

first in the 1982 kharif national uniform variety trial, based on yield at 15 sites that suffered various levels of drought. It outperformed local and national checks at Bhubaneswar, Jeypore, and Sambalpur in Orissa; Jabalpur, Rewa, and Waraseoni in Madhya Pradesh; Faizabad and Varanasi in Uttar Pradesh; and Kanke and Hazaribagh in Bihar (Table 2).

IET7564 and IET7566 performed well in minikit tests on rainfed uplands in Tanjavur (Tamil Nadu) and in East and West Godavari (Andhra Pradesh). □

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Pest management and control DISEASES

Detection of spherical and bacilliform virus particles in tungro-infected rice plants by leafhopper transmission

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Rice tungro disease is a virus complex caused by rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* can transmit both virus particles. GLH can transmit RTSV from plants infected with RTSV alone, but cannot transmit RTBV from plants infected with RTBV alone. RTBV can be transmitted by GLH carrying RTSV.

Rice plants infected with RTSV do not show definite symptoms and may look healthy. Plants infected with RTBV are moderately stunted and discolored. If infected with both particles, plants show severe stunting and discoloration.

Virus particles present in the infected plant can be detected by serology and electron microscopy, but both methods require expensive and sometimes sophisticated equipment that is unavailable at most institutions in developing nations. We developed a simple method of detecting rice tungro virus particles in infected plants on the basis of symptomatology and transmission characteristics of each particle.

Rice plants infected with both particles or RTBV alone were identified first. One-month-old TN 1 plants previously inoculated with tungro using *N. virescens* were sorted by symptoms. Plants with typical tungro symptoms were separated from those without symptoms and exposed to virus-free adult leafhoppers for 24 h acquisition access.

Insects from each virus source plant were then used to inoculate 7-d-old TN1 seedlings in test tubes. The inoculated seedlings were transplanted in pots and kept in the greenhouse for symptom development. Infected rice plants that gave positive transmission were identified as infected with both RTSV and

RTBV. Those that gave negative transmission were identified as plants infected with RTBV alone.

Plants infected with RTSV alone were identified next. Virus-free leafhoppers were given 24 h access to each healthy-looking plant inoculated with RTSV alone, followed by an 8 h or overnight acquisition access to previously identified RTBV-infected plants. The insects were then used to inoculate 7-d-old TN1 seedlings as above. Plants that gave posi-

tive transmission were identified as RTSV-infected while those that gave negative transmission were identified as healthy plants.

In this experiment, TN1 seedlings were inoculated with tungro using plants infected with both virus particles. Sixteen inoculated plants with moderate stunting and discoloration were tested: 2 plants had both RTBV and RTSV and 14 had RTBV alone. Fourteen symptomless plants inoculated with RTSV done were

used for RTSV detection: 12 plants had RTSV and 2 were healthy.

To test the accuracy of this method, the virus particles present in each plant were counterchecked serologically with a latex test. Results of the serological test showed that the method was accurate.

This method takes about 10 d to detect RTBV-infected plants and another 10 d to detect RTSV. In contrast, results by serology and electron microscopy are obtained in only a few hours. □

Quality of rice grains from sheath rot-affected plants

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Sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium* (= *Sarocladium*) *oryzae* Sawada is a major rice disease in India. We recorded changes in grain quality caused by the disease.

Trials with ADT31 and ADT36, both popular varieties in Tamil Nadu, were conducted during 1982 kuruvai. The disease intensity was arbitrarily classified into 5 grades (0, 3, 5, 7, 9) based upon the lesions on the leaf sheath near the panicle. 0 indicated no infection; 9 indicated the boot leaf sheath was completely infected and the panicle could not emerge. No grains formed in plants scoring 9.

Rice grains were harvested from individual plants with various disease intensity levels. Grains also were collected from

Changes in rice grain quality due to sheath rot incidence in 2 rice cultivars.

Disease intensity grade	Discolored grains				1000-grain wt (g)		Seed germination (%)		Protein content (%) of ADT36
	no./panicle		%panicle						
	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	
0	1	2	0.9	1.4	15.7	15.7	94	97	8.0
3	19	54	18.1	38.3	12.3	15.3	89	92	7.5
5	60	78	66.7	67.8	6.3	11.5	76	81	4.4
7	85	94	97.7	93.1	4.9	8.7	58	63	2.2
9	^a								

^aNo grains were formed.

healthy plants. One hundred panicles were collected for each disease intensity category.

Discolored and healthy grains from each panicle were counted. The 1,000-grain weight was measured by taking 4 samples in each category. Germination of seeds from each category was assessed by using the roll towel method and 400 seeds for each infection level. Protein content of ADT36 grains was assessed by estimating total nitrogen content by the micro-Kjeldahl method and multiplying it by 6.25. Two independent experiments, each with four replications, were conducted.

Disease of the boot leaf sheath caused discolored grains (see table). Although many different causes of grain discoloration have been reported, this is the first time that *Acrocyndrium oryzae* has been reported as a cause. Attempts to isolate the fungus from the discolored grains failed, which suggests that the fungus causes grain discoloration by inducing a physiological change.

The disease reduced the 1,000-grain weight and caused poor grain filling, which reduced seed germination (see table). Protein content of the grains was also affected. □

Leaf scald disease of rice in Karnataka, India

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Leaf scald disease of rice caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* was observed for the first time in Karnataka in Oct 1982 on Intan rice. Intan was very susceptible to the disease and had lesions covering more than 50% of the leaf area. Seed

Table 1. Incidence of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* on seeds from Karnataka State districts, India (400 seeds tested per sample following blotter method).

District	Samples tested (no.)	Infected samples (no.)	Samples (no.) at given range (%) of infection						
			0.5-5	6-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-64
Belgaum	2	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—
Bellari	1	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Chikmagalur	3	1	—	—	—	—	1	—	—
Chitradurga	4	3	2	—	1	—	—	—	—
Dharwar	5	1	—	—	1	—	—	—	—
Hassan	7	4	3	1	—	—	—	—	—
Kodagu	5	5	—	—	2	—	1	1	1
Mandya	3	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mysore	20	19	9	7	1	2	—	—	—
Total	50	31	18	8	5	2	2	1	1